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Facilities Management Of Football Stadiums: It's Implications And Customer Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

Quality is one of the most expected aspects by customers of almost all service products. Quality is objective when it is related to external tangible features which can be measured factually. Subjective quality is rated when a customer's imagination, personal experiences, emotions, expectations and attitudes are taken into account. The most common reason for dissatisfaction is the difference between an objective and the subjective evaluation of quality. Service as is any activity or benefit that one party offers to another which is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything, and it may or may not be tied to a physical product. Services are a continuous process of on-going interactions between customers and service providers comprising a number of intangible activities provided as premium solutions to the problems of customers and including the physical and financial resources and any other useful elements of the system involved in providing these services. The present paper is centered on overview, problems and challenges of facility management (fm); implications for facilities management of stadium and customer satisfaction.

Keywords: customer satisfaction, facilities management, Stadium

INTRODUCTION

Facility management is the concept that has grown the most in Europe in the last twenty years, being increasingly recognized its capacity to support business, allowing to create value in the organizations through the integration of the services and the processes that support the core business of organizations. It's considered that FM is the answer to coordination, management and development of all the non-core activities of the organization, making possible a bigger efficiency in terms of investment and cost control. The British Institute of Facilities Management (1999) defines FM as "the practice of coordinating the physical workplace with the people and work of an organisation". This simple and well-focused expression of FM does not, however, stress the contribution that well-managed facilities can make to an organisation. FM, a term that Becker (1990) uses to encompass the activities in planning, designing and managing complex facilities such as offices, hospitals, and schools, differs from architecture and interior design, at least as they have been practiced historically, in the following way: facility management refers to buildings in use, to the planning, design, and management of occupied buildings and their associated

building systems, equipment, and furniture to enable and (one hopes) to enhance the organisation's ability to meet its business or programmatic objectives. FM thus refers to organisational effectiveness.

In 1993, the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS) FM skills panel considered FM to consist of three distinct but interrelated areas:

- i. The management of support services;
- ii. The management of property; and
- iii. The management of information technology.

Thompson (1991) describes a generic FM department, which he considers as having four primary functions:

- i. Real estate and building construction
- ii. Building operations and maintenance
- iii. Facility planning; and
- iv. General/office services

The review of literature suggests that the key components that impact on FM implementation are a synergistic blend of "hard" and "soft" issues. This concept therefore comprises both production oriented and user relations-oriented elements (Varcoe 1992). This perspective is exemplified by the work of Becker (1990), Williams (1996) and Douglas (1996). However, whichever definition of FM is favoured, it is clear that FM is an umbrella term under which a wide range of property and user related functions may be brought together for the benefit of the organisation and its employees as a whole. Therefore, the aim of the FM should be not just to optimise running costs of buildings, but to raise the efficiency and suitability of the management of support services for people and processes, in order that the mission and goals of the organisation may be achieved at the best combination of efficiency, cost and quality. The present paper is an overview, problems and challenges of facility management (fm); implications of facilities management of stadium.

Principles of Facilities Management

FM is fundamentally a management function, as the following definition (Becker, 1990) suggests: "FM is responsible for co-ordinating all efforts related to planning, designing, and managing buildings and their systems, equipment and furniture to enhance the organisation's ability to compete successfully in a rapidly changing world". Oladejo (2014) cited in Chinedu N.P. Oladejo E.I (2019) stated that "Facilities Management (FM) can be applied to any form of structure or building that houses certain user activities, equipment and furniture in order for it to execute jobs with optimum ease and satisfaction while reducing costs." Tuveson (1998) identifies FM as the co-ordination of the physical workplace with the people and work of an organisation. Thus, the role of FM in organisations is to support the achievement of organisational goals (Anderson, 1996). Pheng (1996) suggests that FM contains four main principles:

- i. The continuous programmed co-ordination of all efforts, namely planning, designing, construction and management of facilities towards enhancing the working environment of the people and the organisation's ability to meet its business objectives;
- ii. The total integration of a diverse field of disciplines of business, architecture, behavioural and engineering science under one entity in an organisation to oversee all facilities functions previously controlled by independent departments;
- iii. The management of activities proactively rather than the management of facilities reactively; and
- iv. A business concept where FM policies and procedures are guided by organisational goals and objectives as well as available resources.

From a macro perspective, FM is a multidisciplinary, but an integrated function that generally involves more than one department in a large organisation. Therefore, FM- in its widest possible sense - is concerned with the dynamic interaction between an organisation's personnel, process and place (Laird, 1994).

Revolution in FM

FM is one of the main cost-cutting initiatives of the 1970s and 1980s when organisations began to outsource their core services (BIFM, 2012; Mohd-Noor and Pitt, 2009a). In the last three decades, FM has established itself as a key service sector, with a diverse and highly competitive market of FM contractors, in-house FM teams, FM vendors, FM consultants and professional FM institutions (Nutt, 1999; Tay and Ooi, 2001). FM was traditionally viewed as the poor relation between the real estate and construction professions, often conjuring images of maintenance plants, caretaking and cleaning (Atkins and Brooks, 2000). Becker (1990) believes that FM encompasses all areas of an organization's activities and can be seen as a series of linked activities involving the co-ordination of all efforts relating to the planning, designing and managing of an organisation's physical resources. Then (1990) contradicts Becker's perception that FM mainly covers the physical equipment of the building as he believes that the practice is concerned with the delivery of an enabling workplace environment, the optimum functional space that supports the business processes and human resources. The success of FM at a corporate level can be seen in how it contributes to the delivery of strategic and operational objectives on a day-to-day basis (Mohd-Noor and Pitt, 2009a). Its scope of discipline covers all aspects of property, space, environment control, health and safety, and support services (Alexander, 1999). More often than not, the FM remit is interpreted as maintenance management, space management and accommodation standards; project management for new built and alterations to the general premises; management of the building stock and the administration of associated support services (Hinks and McNay, 1999). From another perspective, FM is also seen as a management of cost-efficiency rather than a method by which to achieve multi-dimensional enhancement of business competitiveness. Many still view FM in collective terms, which lumps together all building facilities and services within the organisation. It becomes a non-core department, supporting services and, more importantly, the innovation that can be brought about by improving the management of services (Pitt and Hinks, 2001). However, FM is not just about delivering services in the most effective ways, it is also about providing them in an ever-evolving world/industry (Mohd-Noor and Pitt, 2009b).

Scope of FM Services

It is important to clarify the distinctive features of FM and focus on its specific roles in managing resources, environments and services to provide logistics support to the operations of organisations and also contribute to the success of the core business (Nutt, 1999). Many organisations have re-evaluated the contributions of FM to making a business successful, recognising the business consequences of poorly managed facilities and searching for value that can be added through effective planning and management (Alexander, 1996). High profile events such as the British Institute of Facilities Management (BIFM) Annual Awards for Innovation reflect a growing recognition of innovation in the FM sector (Cardellino and Finch, 2006).

There are mainly two types of FM services, namely hard and soft FM. These are the services required to support the operation of the service asset (Scottish Government, 2005). Hard FM relates to the services intended for the actual fabric and building systems and might also be considered to incorporate the more traditional FM services (IFMA, 2012). The scope for respective service is introduced by the IFMA (2012) and BIFM (2012) as follows:

- i. Hard FM services include maintenance of buildings, engineering, air conditioning system, electrical system, plumbing system, fire-fighting and fire prevention system, security system, building control system, building management system and building fabric works.
- ii. Soft FM focuses on the maintenance of catering, cleaning, health and safety, landscaping and internal plants, security, pest control, handyman, waste disposal and some other support services.

The IFMA (2012) also introduces another Additional Services category for other services, namely printing, reception services, information systems, space planning, and management services such as business risk assessment, business continuity planning, benchmarking, performance management and also contract procurement. There is also an overlap of services by IFMA in the Additional Services category, which some companies categorise as soft FM.

Problems and Challenges of Facility Management (FM)

Samad (2007) declares that the first and foremost issue in handling FM is to determine the right department to be in charge of handling government buildings, as this involves public assets and funds. The confusion of selecting the responsible ministry or department to perform a full surveillance of FM practice in developing countries indicates that the sector is in need of strategic organisation and planning. The lack of an FM government body also restricts the evaluation of FM industry development in developing countries. There is also a problem in outsourcing for local expertise to provide an immediate response to any failure of service, as well as a lack of FM practitioners in the local market who can provide advice or assistance in the implementation of FM. For instance, in Malaysia, the key issue faced by FM is the low service quality (Ruslan, 2007). The implementation of FM is considered to be too late for some properties, as at present there are many aging buildings with high levels of deterioration. FM may help in standardizing the future maintenance allocation required but this, however, may not contribute to minimisation of maintenance costs if the building services are in poor condition due to improper maintenance carried out in the past. The real challenge of FM lies in the lack of standards that can be used to measure the quality level and performance of both traditional and integrated FM applied by building or property management companies. The slow pace of regulating appropriate FM standards or regulations is another factor that requires immediate action. A good level of planning for FM may help in standardising the future maintenance allocation required and planning for the strategic maintenance approach.

Facilities Management of Stadium

Facilities Management can be seen as a solution to an integrated and systematic management of existing services in stadiums fitting it in building management and business models existing in this kind of asset. With the ever increasing growth of the sport business sector's importance over the last few years, the need has emerged to urgently turn professional sports clubs into corporate businesses (Desbores, 2007). Consequently, sport clubs pay increasing attention to the range of service they can offer with regard to the best business development opportunities. Arenas or stadiums play a major role in such potential development opportunities. The optimisation of this resource started with soccer clubs offering business customers targeted services. Since then, mass customers have also been addressed by means of new services designed to encourage them to visit the stadium more often and to make use of the related facilities (Guenzi, 2007). By enlarging the range of services provided in and outside the stadium, sport clubs have become multiservice companies. In the course of this development, the last few decades have seen traditional sports venues, such as indoor sports sites, replaced with modern event centres in numerous cities worldwide (Siegfried and Zimbalist, 2000). These multi-purpose stadiums provide room for large events of any kind. By offering a comprehensive food and beverage service as well as an expanded collateral program, they evoke the character of leisure-oriented venues. In contrast to soccer stadiums, which are primarily supported by municipal or local governments, the majority of these multi-purpose stadiums are privately financed. Consequently, it is imperative for the operating and marketing concept to be designed and implemented in a profit-oriented manner. Frequent and continuous utilisation by the primary tenant (e.g., a sport association) and an offer of top events in the fields of culture, sports, music and entertainment constitute the essential parameters of a stadium's economic success. From the stadium operator's viewpoint, visitor potential can only be exploited if the stadium offers a large number and broad variety of events which increases proceeds from ticket sales or advertisements or the allocation of broadcasting rights. Furthermore, utilisation is affected by the attendance figures at events, as defined by the indirect network effects concept (Katz and Shapiro, 1985). An important determinant of attendance is customer satisfaction (Greenwell et al., 2006), which mediates the relationship between service quality and behavioural intentions (e.g., Anderson and Sullivan, 1993). Specifically, customers' evaluations of service quality have influenced emotional satisfaction assessments and in turn, specific behaviours such as customer loyalty (e.g., Fornell et al., 1996), customer retention (e.g., Garbarino and Johnson, 1999),

willingness to pay (Homburg et al., 2005) and price tolerance (Anderson, 1996). Stadium operators' primary interest should therefore be to increase attendees' satisfaction by improving the perceived service value (Gudergan and Ellis, 2007) so that visitors are willing to attend events regularly and recommend visiting the stadium to other persons, Figure 2.2 shows a typical visitor route during an event in a stadium. Improving the services within this route could improve customer satisfaction. Knowledge about visitor satisfaction and its determining factors are consequently of fundamental significance for operating companies. Despite its apparent importance, research literature on this subject is very scarce. There are only a few studies in the sport management research field that assess a sports facility's ability to influence customers' attendance or attendance intentions. Wakefield et al. (1996).

Figure 2.1: Typical visitor route during an event (Source: Hock)

Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Service Quality (SQ) and Customer Satisfaction (CS) are very important concepts that business organisations must understand if they want to remain competitive and grow. In today's competitive environment, delivering high quality service is the key for a sustainable competitive advantage. Quality service delivery will not only depend on organizational practices, but has to do with the approach and attitude of both organization and employees.(Aguome, Ogbuefi, and Egolum 2019) Customer Service

forms the foundation of any successful business as it leads to repeat purchase, brand loyalty, and positive word of mouth (Angelova&Zekiri, 2011).

Companies win or lose based on what percentage of their customers they can keep. Success is largely about the retention of customers, which again depends on the CS level. It would be a great help to be able to comprehensively measure the quality of products and services by relating the measures of quality to real customer behaviour. Some companies get feedback about CS through the percentage of complaints and some through non-systematic surveys, but some do not measure CS at all, because “the system would not add anything useful and is very time-consuming” (Chotipanich, 2004). Most markets are very competitive, and in order to survive, organisations need to produce products and services of a very good quality that yield highly satisfied and loyal customers. Fidelis-Umeh, D., Emoh, F.I. &Ewurum N.I.(2017) noted that organisations can only win by creating and delivering superior value which involves understanding customer value and creating customer value through the provision of core and relevant facilities (buildings, infrastructure and support services etc.) tailored towards customer satisfaction. Many practitioners and researchers have investigated a range of different customer attitudes that influence both intentions and behaviours relating to loyalty. Customer attitudes have included customer satisfaction, customer value, price perceptions, the quality of the relationship and service quality.

Summary and Conclusion

In the growing service sector there is still the most problematic challenge of how to deal with service quality. Quality is one of the most expected aspects by customers of almost all service products (Urban, 2009). Before quality can be managed it must be defined (Rondeau, et al., 2006). Coming up with a precise definition of the quality of services is complicated because quality can be understood and evaluated both objectively and subjectively. Quality is objective when it is related to external tangible features which can be measured factually. Subjective quality is rated when a customer’s imagination, personal experiences, emotions, expectations and attitudes are taken into account (Bagdoniene, Hopeniene, 2004; Langviniene, Vengriene, 2005). The most common reason for dissatisfaction is the difference between an objective and the subjective evaluation of quality (Bagdoniene, Hopeniene, 2004). In trying to define service quality, there is need to look at the words separately first. There are several definitions regarding the concepts of service. Services are deeds, processes, and performances (Parasuraman et al. 1985). Service as is any activity or benefit that one party offers to another which is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything, and it may or may not be tied to a physical product (Kotler et. al., 1999). Services are a continuous process of on-going interactions between customers and service providers comprising a number of intangible activities provided as premium solutions to the problems of customers and including the physical and financial resources and any other useful elements of the system involved in providing these services (Grönroos, 2004). Quality refers to the matching between customers’ expectations and their experiences (Berry et al., 1988). It is considered as an investment for company or an organisation, where the efforts for its improvement result in an increased clientele, increased levels of purchase from existing customers, and a rise in the company’s profits (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Reichheld & Sasser, 1990; Rust et al., 1995). Quality is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. There are three dimensions of output technical quality, service performance quality, and organization’s mental picture (Gronroos, 2000).Quality involves eliminating ‘internal failures’ (defects before the product leaves the factory) and ‘external failures’ (defects after product use); (Garvin, 1983). Service Quality had ten dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, competence, access, courtesy, communication, creditability, security, understanding/knowing the customers and tangibility. These ten dimensions were cut down to five namely, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

They are as follows (Parasuraman et al., 1988):

- i. Tangibility: This dimension includes the appearance of physical facilities, equipment personnel and communication materials used to communicate with customers. Elements within the tangibles dimension are cleanliness, space, atmosphere, appearance of server and location.

- ii. Reliability: It is the ability to perform the promised services dependably and accurately. The elements of reliability are speed, willingness to respond, accuracy and dependability.
- iii. Responsiveness: It is the willingness to help customers, and provide prompt service. Its elements include that of reliability.
- iv. Assurance: It is the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Assurance may be measured using elements of knowledge, communications and caring for the customer.
- v. Empathy: It is the provision of caring individualized attention to customers. Its elements are the same as assurance.

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